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The Role of Social Activities in Educational Institutions in the Socialization Process

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Abstract

In this research, we aimed to examine the social cohesion that folk dances activities have on secondary school students in terms of some variables. The sample of the research which was conducted using general screening model consists of 156 volunteer students who study at randomly selected secondary schools. The scale of social cohesion in sports was used as the data collection tool in the research. As a result of the research, based on the answers given by the secondary school students in the sample to the scale, it was determined that the general arithmetic average of the social skill level obtained by their participation in folk dances was statistically high. In the research, it was also determined that among the students who participated in the folk dance activities in the survey, female students, twelfth grade students, students who participated in folk dance activities for the eighth to eleventh times outside the standard training sessions, and students whose families' level of income was lower than the other students perceived social unity in a higher level than the rest of the students in the sample. Moreover, it was concluded that there was no statistically significant difference between gender, class, and the repetition variables of the folk dance activities outside the standard training sessions with the social cohesion-providing behavior changes, however, there was a significant difference between the income level variables.

Keywords: Folk Dances, Secondary Education, Student, Socialization, Sports.

1. Introduction

Socialization teaches people how to behave in certain situations and thus ensures that people learn and adopt their social roles (Afacan, 2001). Sociology is a scientific discipline which examines the structure of society, its functions, changes taking place according to its functions, and the social problems that arise as a result of these, with unique observations, and links them to some laws and principles (Yetim, 2011), and it can also be described as the sum of all the phases that a person needs to experience from birth, in order to gain acceptance in the society (Erkal, Guven & Ayan, 1998).

In other words, socialization can be defined as the process by which a person learns, internalizes the socio-cultural elements of the environment throughout his or her life, and integrates these with his/her personality under the influence of experiential and meaningful social institutions, and conforms to the social environment in which he or she must be integrated in (Sayin, 1994). In order to talk about socialization, psycho-social learning,

which occurs as a result of the interaction of the individual with other people, must be experienced (Bas & Sarigoz, 2018). The individual effectively learns to adapt to social life in this process. One of the environments in which these learning takes place in the sports environment (Ozdinc, 2005). Learning is an important factor in the socialization of individuals. Individual development, maturation, and growth develops learning (Sahan, 2008).

One of the places where the learning process takes place in the educational institutions. Schools are the institutions where individuals learn their social responsibilities (Sarigoz, 2021). The interaction of an individual with other individuals and their participation in the activities is realized at school (Bacanli, 2005). Sports activities improve individuals' attention, concentration, problem-solving skills, productivity, imagination, adhering to rules and using practical intelligence (Yetim, 2000). Today, sportive activities and human life are almost inseparable. For this reason, sports activities, which are made consciously and systematically at any age, play an important role in keeping people healthy, harmonious, successful and happy and keeping them in a good mood throughout their whole life (Olmez, 2010).

There is a balanced harmony of the body, arms and legs in terms of physical development in the training of folk dances which can be considered among sportive activities. Learning and management of motor skills allows for gradual control of the movements of arms and legs outside everyday life movements (Brown, 1991). Considering that the back and leg muscle strength of people who play folk dances is usually more developed than the ones who do not (Unal, 1992), we can say that folk dances contribute to the motor development of individuals. Folk dances, which show physically basic similarities with other sports branches, are social activities through holding hands and direct contact with other individuals. Folk dances help those who practice them to be a part of a group, to interact socially with other members of the group, to have a sense of belonging through acting in unison and thus development of group dynamics which in turn may help to prevent or reduce some psychological or social problems (Kocaturk, 2005). Dance, which contains sportive movements, is important in terms of providing individuals with social identity and thus contributing to their socialization, as well as being a group of movements. Individuals are happy with the success of the group or dance type they perform, and they can overcome the negativities they have accumulated in the life process with their group friends who share this happiness. When evaluated in this context, these areas, which support and contribute to the discharge and elimination of negative emotions and thoughts that individuals have accumulated in their lives, can also be seen as treatment places by psychiatrists (Tezcan, 1977). From a psychological point of view, dance can give individuals a sense of pleasure and happiness. Participation in dance can undoubtedly be seen as one of the most important methods of overcoming stress, which is called the disease of our age. Engaging in such activities can be seen as an important factor in reducing negative symptoms such as depression and anger (Crews & Landers, 1987). In addition, dance is important in that it contributes to positive personality traits such as confidence and internal control and that these are good for human psychology, being peaceful against the sense of aggression in human nature and providing the individual with the opportunity to relax (Steptoe & Cox, 1988).

In the light of the above information, it is important to determine the contribution of folk dance activities, which are the subject of our study, to the social integrity of individuals. In the research, it will be tried to determine the level of social cohesion perception felt by the students, through some independent variables.

2. Material and Method

The aim of this research was to determine the level of socialization perceived by the secondary school students engaging in folk dances as a part of their sports activities, by taking some variables into account. The general survey model, which is one of the descriptive survey methods, was used in the research. Survey model is defined as "the survey arrangements made on the whole population or a group, a sample, or a sample group to be taken from it in order to make a general judgment about the population consisting of many elements" (Karasar, 2015).

The population of the research consisted of secondary school students who participated in the folk dance group competitions organized in the youth category by the Turkish School Sports Federation in the 2020/2021 academic year. The sample consisted of a total of 156 secondary school students, 47 male and 107 female, who

were randomly selected from the population by the simple random method. The data required in the research were collected using the Social Integration Scale in Sports, which consists of 32 items (Yilmaz, Karli & Yetim, 2006). The reliability coefficient of the scale was calculated as .917. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale was determined to be .899. The scale aims to determine the various levels of social integration in a five-point Likert type by ranking them as (5) Strongly Agree (4) Agree (3) Undecided (2) Disagree (1) Strongly Disagree. High scores obtained from the scale indicate that social integration in sports is positive.

The answers given by the students in the sample group to the scale items depending on the demographic variables were calculated with the help of a statistical package program. In the analysis of the data, the normality test was performed to determine whether the data were suitable for normal distribution. After the test, the skewness (-.220) and kurtosis (1.373) values of the scale were found to be between +1,500 and -1,500. Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) state that the data distribution occurs as a normal distribution when the skewness and kurtosis values are between +1,500 and -1,500. In this context, since the results obtained showed normal distribution, besides descriptive analyses, t-test for pairwise comparisons and Cohen's d data for effect size were examined. For comparisons of three or more groups, one-way ANOVA test was performed, and eta square (η^2) test was applied since we had only one dependent variable in the effect size. The effect sizes of the data were calculated for the independent t-test by using Cohen's d (Cohen, 1988), considering the mean differences .02, 0.5 and 0.8 as small, medium and large effects, and for two-way ANOVA by using eta square (η^2) (Lakens, 2013), considering the mean differences .01, .06 and .14 as small, medium and large effects. The statistical significance level was accepted as Alpha (α), and the error level as accepted as $p < 0.05$. The results obtained from the distributions were tabulated, the findings were interpreted, and necessary solutions were suggested. The option intervals and the general evaluation of the scales used in the study were calculated as follows.

$$SA = \frac{EYD - EDD}{SS} = \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,8$$

SA:	Option range	1.00 - 1.79:	Low
EYD:	Maximum value	1.80 - 2.59:	Below medium
EDD:	Minimum value	2.60 - 3.39:	Medium
SS:	Number of options	3.40 - 4.19:	Above medium
		4.20 - 5.00:	High

3. Findings

In this section, statistical findings on the data obtained from secondary school students in the survey are presented.

Table 1: Levels of social cohesion that the students perceive through folk dances

Social Cohesion Behaviors in Sports	N	$\bar{X}$	Ss
	156	4.47	.66

It was determined that the social skill perceptions obtained by participation of folk dances in sports by the secondary school students who participated in the research was of a high level, with a general arithmetic average of 4.47 points.

Table 2: Depending on the gender variable, the social integration status of the students participating in the folk dances with the folk dance sport

Gender variable	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	t-	p>.05	Cohen's d
Male	47	30.1	4.40	.75	152	-.797	.426	.001
Female	107	69.9	4.49	.59				
Total	156	100	4.47	.66				

No statistically significant difference between female and male students was found ($t_{(152)} = -.797$, $p > .05$) from the answers given by the secondary school students who participated in the survey.

Table 3: Depending on the variable of grade level in which they study, the social integration status of the students participating in folk dances with folk dance sports

Grade	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	The source of variance	Sum of squares	Sd	Average of squares	F	p>.05	η^2
Ninth	16	10.3	4.37	.82	Intergroup	.393	3	.131	.29	.831	.005
Tenth	20	12.8	4.40	1.05	Intragroup	67.956	152	.447	3		
Eleventh	52	33.3	4.48	.55	Total	68.349	155				
Twelfth	68	43.6	4.52	.55							
Total	156	100	4.47	.66							

No statistically significant difference between students in different grades was found ($F_{(3,152)} = .293$, $p > .05$) from the answers given by the secondary school students who participated in the survey.

Table 4: Social integration status of students participating in folk dances depending on the situation of performing folk dances more than once.

Repetition	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	The source of variance	Sum of squares	Sd	Average of squares	F	p>.05	η^2
1-3	46	29.5	4.46	.51	Intergroup	.601	3	.200	.450	.718	.008
4-7	44	28.2	4.45	.46	Intragroup	67.748	152	.446			
8-11	9	5.8	4.57	.74	Total	68.349	155				
11 and above	57	36.5	4.42	.73							
Total	156	100	4.47	.66							

No statistically significant difference was found in terms of their perception of social integrity between students who repeated their folk dance activities outside the trainings and those who did not ($F_{(3,152)} = .450$, $p > .05$).

Table 5: Social integration status of students participating in folk dances depending on their families' income levels.

Level of income	N	%	$\bar{X}$	Ss	The source of variance	Sum of squares	SD	Average of squares	F	p<.05	η^2
a) Low	102	65.4	4.55	.57	Intergroup	8.72	2	4.364	11.199	.000	.127
b) Medium	44	28.2	4.51	.71	Intragroup	59.621	153	.390			
c) High	10	6.4	3.57	.69	Total	68.349	155				
Total	156	100	4.47	.66							

Tukey
a,b- c

A statistically significant difference was found between the social cohesion perceptions of the students depending on the level of income of their families ($F_{(2,153)} = 11.199$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .127$). As a result of the Tukey test, which was conducted to determine between which groups the significant difference was, it can be said that families with low and middle income levels are more socially integrated than families with high income levels.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

It has been determined that the general arithmetic average of the social skill perceptions of the secondary school students participating in the research obtained by their participation in folk dances is statistically at a high level. It can be said that individuals' self-confidence is completed by getting rid of selfishness and strengthening the awareness of cooperation with each other, and the development of their sense of responsibility thanks to their participation in sports activities (Biskin, 2001). The need of individuals to be a social being is at least as important as the desire to be sportive and healthy. At the same time, dance is effective in personal and social development as well as in gaining personality by instilling emotions such as willpower, determination to succeed, and the desire to progress into the individual, making the destructive, aggressive, hurtful and intolerable impulses that exist in the human structure positive (Tercan, 2016). When the relationship between physical activity and educational success of the dancing classes and the non-dancing classes was examined in the USA, it was seen that academic and social success was more in favor of the dancing classes (Robinson, 2018). When the literature is examined, it is stated in some studies on the subject that the effect of sportive activities on socialization is positive (Akcalar, 2007; Cakmakci, 2001; Hacicaferoglu, Hacicaferoglu, Kayhan & Doganay, 2017; Okmen, 2003; Ozturk, 2016; Sahan, 2008; Tuncalp, 2011; Zeynep, 2010).

In the study, it was determined from the answers given to the scale by the students that there was no statistically significant difference between the female and male students in terms of the gender variable. In this case, it can be said that the thoughts of the athletes regarding social cohesion are equal to one another in accordance with the gender variable; however, females were found to perceive folk dance activities more spiritually developing than competitive sports, when looked at the arithmetic points they received. In the literature, it is stated in some of the research that the level of socialization of women by sport activities is higher than that of men (Aytan, 2010; Theberge, 2000; Yilmaz, 2006). Another research indicates that men do more sports activities compared to women to socialize (Ozdinc, 2005). In contrast, there are also some research results indicating that sports have an equal level of socialization impact on both females and males (Tuncalp, 2011). The literature presents us research results that sports activities have a statistically significant relationship between gender variable and socialization perception (Aytan, 2010; Yilmaz, 2006), but there are also results which have stated completely the opposite (Kaya, 2003).

It was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between the social integration perceptions of students depending on the variable of grade. Therefore, it can be said that the level of social cohesion the students perceived through the folk dances during the research are close to one another, regardless of their grade. Nevertheless, when the total arithmetic scores are examined, it is determined that the students who study in the twelfth grade perceive more social cohesion than the other students. It can be said that the level of perception of socialization perceived by the students who study in the upper grades is higher because of students' being at an age that allows them to make their own decision and choose their own friends. In a related research, it is stated that the effect of the grade of the students participating in nature sports on the social integration is between medium and high levels, and there is not a statistically significant difference (Yilmaz, 2006). In another study, however, it was stated that the higher grade of the students was, the lesser socialization points they had and there was no statistically significant difference (Aytan, 2010).

It was determined that there was no statistically significant difference between students' perceptions of social cohesion due to the variable of repeating the folk dances outside normal training sessions. When looked at the answers given, it was determined that students who exhibited this sport 8 to 11 times outside normal training sessions as an arithmetic score perceived more social cohesion than the others. It can be said that it can help provide joy and stability in troubled lives and alleviate the tensions caused by violence and bullying that may occur in schools (Robinson, 2018), and it can be said that it is important in realizing social cohesion by coping with negativities such as anxiety that may occur during the life process (Hacicaferoglu, Hacicaferoglu & Secer, 2015). Participation in physical activity positively affects the individual's ability to socialize and build social relationships (Reppucci, 1987). In this context, it can be said that the individuals who are frequently engaged in sports activities are more active in establishing social relations and are more successful in their profession than the participants who are engaged in these activities less frequently (Ozturk, 2016; Yilmaz, 2006). As the years of

doing sport increase, it has positive effects on the socialization of the individual (Kizmaz, 2004). In addition, it can be said that cultural activities such as folk dances included in the recreation programs implemented by the educational institutions will contribute to the socialization of the students by increasing their commitment to their schools and their surroundings, positively affecting group formation, group dynamics and group solidarity among students and thus affecting their academic performances positively (Kocaturk, 2005). It can be said that participation in physical activity, which does not have a large number of training sessions, will contribute positively to the individual's social development and ability to establish social relations (Reppucci, 1987; Ozturk, Akin, & Damar, 2016). On the other hand, it is seen that there are also research results in which the socialization integrity is high, although the number of training is less (Hacicaferoglu & Sumer, 2019).

It was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between students' perceptions of social cohesion depending on the income levels of their families. It is also seen that the income level groups of the students are close to each other. On the other hand, it was determined that the students with families having a lower and middle income level perceived more social cohesion with this sport branch as an arithmetic score. Considering the research conducted by Kotan et al. (2009), it is stated that the rate of doing sports increases as the income level increases. It can be said that as the family income level of the students being athlete increases, it can lead to an increase in the social and sportive activity opportunities and diversity of the students in parallel with the improvement of the socio-economic conditions (Gullu et al., 2016). Some research results on the subject show that the income levels of the participants are low (Ozdinc, 2005; Tuncalp, 2011), medium (Yilmaz, 2006), and high (Zeynep, 2010) in various studies.

As a result, in this research, which aimed to determine the social cohesion imposed by folk dance activities on the secondary school students in terms of some variables, it was determined that the level of social skills acquired by participation in the branches of folk dances was statistically high, based on the answers given by the secondary school students in the sample. It was also determined that female students, twelfth grade students, the students who were engaged in folk dance activities eight to ten times more than the normal training sessions, and the students whose families' income level was low and medium perceived more social cohesion in terms of arithmetic score, in folk dance activities compared to the other students. It was also found that there was no statistically significant difference between variables such as gender, grade and the repetition of folk dance activities outside normal training sessions by the students and social cohesion providing behavior; nonetheless, there was a significant difference between students of different family income levels.

4.1. Suggestions

It can be said that folk dance activities provide positive contributions to the socialization process and that the individuals who are trained in this branch can experience a more effective socialization process. In this context, folk dance activities, which combine music, rhythm and physical activities, should be taught as a separate folk dance class for students in secondary education institutions together with their conventional physical education lessons. In addition, the age groups and the educational levels of the students who will participate in this sports branch may be different, so the people who will teach this class should take the pedagogical formation training. Sports and cultural events usually held at the end of educational periods are required to be repeated more than once a year. Thus, more awareness can be raised about the folk dance sport, which can contribute effectively to the socialization process of individuals.

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